

Reducing the Measurement Footprint in the Characterization of Low-Loss Materials Using the Flanged-Waveguide Measurement Geometry

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Abstract — The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate how the flanged-waveguide material-characterization technique, originally designed to characterize lossy materials only, can be extended to accurately extract permittivity and permeability of low-loss materials. Provided in this paper is a summary of the flanged-waveguide technique. This is followed by a discussion of how time-domain gating can be utilized to mitigate the error introduced by waves reflected from the edges of the flanges. Furthermore, it is demonstrated that by utilizing time-domain gating, the cross-sectional dimensions of the flanges can be significantly reduced. Lastly, material measurement results of plexiglass are provided to validate the time-domain gating technique.

1 INTRODUCTION

Coaxial and waveguide probes have been studied for the past 30 years. Their uses include nondestructive material evaluation, subsurface crack detection, and even hyperthermia treatment [1–3]. Existing research has focused on obtaining the reflection coefficient, using a single probe, of an unknown material backed by a dielectric half-space or a PEC. While this scenario is ideal for determining the dielectric constant of an unknown material, it suffers when one wants to determine permeability because it lacks two (or more) independent measurements. The ideal apparatus would provide the ability to simultaneously measure both the reflection and transmission coefficients since they are independent over all wavelengths. Such an apparatus is the flanged-waveguide structure [4] (see Fig. 1). One of the requirements of the flanged-waveguide measurement technique is that the material under test (MUT) be lossy enough (or the PEC flanges large enough) to ensure that waves reflected from the edges of the flanges (henceforth referred to as two-way reflection error) are not detected. That is, the flanges (of finite cross section) used in the measurement can be safely approximated as infinite in

extent as long as the two-way reflection error is low enough in amplitude to be in the noise of detector. The paper states that in order to accurately measure a low-loss material like plexiglass (i.e., sufficiently mitigate two-way reflection error), flanges on the order of 200 in. (5.08 m) \times 200 in. (5.08 m) are required to satisfy the infinite-flange assumption [4].

The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate, using the dominant TE₁₀ rectangular-waveguide mode only, how the flanged-waveguide material-characterization technique can be extended to accurately extract permittivity and permeability of low-loss materials. First, a summary of the characterization technique is provided (Section 2). Second, the key contribution of this research is discussed, i.e., how time-domain gating can be employed to mitigate the two-way reflection error of low-loss MUT's (Section 3). Furthermore, it is demonstrated that by utilizing time-domain gating, the flange dimensions (i.e., the footprint of the measurement apparatus) can be significantly reduced. Lastly, material measurement results of plexiglass, performed at X-band using 12 in. (30.48 cm) \times 12 in. (30.48 cm) and 6 in. (15.24 cm) \times 6 in. (15.24 cm) flanges, are presented to validate the proposed time-domain gating technique and to demonstrate flange-footprint reduction (Section 4).

2 FLANGED-WAVEGUIDE MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE

Consider the geometry depicted in Fig. 1—two flanged-rectangular waveguides sandwich an unknown material of complex permittivity ϵ and permeability μ . Note that ϵ and μ cannot be directly measured. In most cases their values must be obtained by fitting the theoretical expressions of measurable quantities (in this case, the reflection S_{11}^{thy} and transmission S_{21}^{thy} coefficients) to experimental data (S_{11}^{meas} and S_{21}^{meas}). The purpose of this section is to derive theoretical expressions for these quantities.

In order to find theoretical expressions for S_{11}^{thy} and S_{21}^{thy} , expressions for the transverse electric and magnetic fields must be found in the waveguide

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Figure 1: Measurement geometry of the flanged-waveguide apparatus.

and parallel-plate regions of Fig. 1. The transverse fields in the waveguide regions take the common form (assuming a guide-centered origin and dominant-mode expansion only)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}^t &= \hat{\mathbf{y}} \Gamma \frac{\pi}{a} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) e^{-\gamma z} + \hat{\mathbf{y}} \Gamma \frac{\pi}{a} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) e^{\gamma z} \\ \mathbf{H}^t &= \hat{\mathbf{x}} \Gamma \frac{-\pi}{aZ} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) e^{-\gamma z} - \hat{\mathbf{x}} \Gamma \frac{-\pi}{aZ} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) e^{\gamma z} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

when $z < 0$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}^t &= \hat{\mathbf{y}} \Gamma \frac{\pi}{a} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) e^{-\gamma(z-d)} \\ \mathbf{H}^t &= \hat{\mathbf{x}} \Gamma \frac{-\pi}{aZ} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) e^{-\gamma(z-d)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

when $z > d$. In the above field expressions, γ and Z are the propagation constant and the wave impedance, respectively [5], $\Gamma = S_{11}^{\text{thy}}$, and $\mathbf{T} = S_{21}^{\text{thy}}$.

The transverse magnetic field in the parallel-plate region can be found by replacing the waveguide apertures by equivalent magnetic currents \mathcal{M}_1 and \mathcal{M}_2 in accordance with Love's equivalence principle [5]:

$$\mathbf{H}^t = \frac{1}{j\omega\mu\varepsilon} (k^2 + \nabla_t \nabla \cdot) \mathbf{F} \quad (3)$$

where $k = \omega(\varepsilon\mu)^{1/2}$ is the material's wavenumber, ∇_t is the transverse gradient operator, and \mathbf{F} is the electric vector potential, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{F} &= \int_{S'} \varepsilon \mathcal{M}_1(\boldsymbol{\rho}') G^t(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z | \boldsymbol{\rho}', 0) dS' \\ &+ \int_{S'} \varepsilon \mathcal{M}_2(\boldsymbol{\rho}') G^t(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z | \boldsymbol{\rho}', d) dS' \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Here, G^t is the transverse parallel-plate Green's function shown in [4], $\boldsymbol{\rho} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}x + \hat{\mathbf{y}}y$, $\boldsymbol{\rho}' = \hat{\mathbf{x}}x' + \hat{\mathbf{y}}y'$,

and S' represents the cross-sectional areas of the waveguide apertures, i.e., $-a/2 \leq x' \leq a/2$ and $-b/2 \leq y' \leq b/2$.

Having found expressions for the transverse fields in the waveguide and parallel-plate regions of Fig. 1, a system of coupled magnetic field integral equations (MFIE's) can be formed by enforcing the continuity of transverse magnetic fields at $z = 0$ and $z = d$:

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \Gamma) \frac{-\pi}{aZ} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) &= \frac{(k^2 + \nabla_t \nabla \cdot)}{j\omega\mu\varepsilon} \mathbf{F}(x, y, 0) \\ \mathbf{T} \frac{-\pi}{aZ} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{a}\right) &= \frac{(k^2 + \nabla_t \nabla \cdot)}{j\omega\mu\varepsilon} \mathbf{F}(x, y, d) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

These coupled MFIE's can be solved using the Method of Moments (MoM) with the dominant-waveguide mode used for expansion and testing. The MoM transforms (5) into a 2×2 matrix equation

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma \\ \mathbf{T} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where A_{11} and A_{22} represent the "self" terms, i.e., the source and observer are at the same location. The off-diagonal elements A_{12} and A_{21} are "coupling" terms. They model how a source at aperture 2 influences the fields at aperture 1 (A_{12}) and vice versa (A_{21}). Reciprocity dictates that $A_{12} = A_{21}$; the symmetry of the geometry in Fig. 1 stipulates that $A_{11} = A_{22}$.

3 TIME-DOMAIN GATING

As discussed above, the flanged-waveguide technique (reviewed in Section 2) was originally designed to characterize lossy materials only. This requirement ensured that the effects of two-way reflection error were mitigated. In [4], the authors show that the dominant mode in the parallel-plate region (a TE^p mode) has an asymptotic radial-field behavior proportional to $\exp(-jkR)/R^{1/2}$. With this relation and the dynamic range of the network analyzer, the cross-sectional dimensions of the flanges can be calculated so that two-way reflection error is negligible. As expected, for lossy materials like ECCOSORB® FGM-125 and FGM-40, relatively small flange dimensions on the order of 12 in. \times 12 in. are sufficient and the technique is very practical. However, when one performs the above calculation for a low-loss material like plexiglass, flange dimensions on the order of 200 in. \times 200 in. are required to mitigate two-way reflection error. These flange dimensions are impractical and thus the technique as presented in [4] cannot be used for low-loss materials.

Figure 2: Time-domain $|S_{11}|$ of plexiglass measured using 12 in. \times 12 in. flanges.

As eluded to above, an elegant solution to this limitation is to time-gate out the reflections from the flange edges. Figure 2 shows a plot of $|S_{11}|$ in the time domain for a sample of plexiglass measured using 12 in. \times 12 in. flanges. The first reflection from the flange edges is clearly resolved at approximately 1.6 ns, which agrees nicely with the time (1.64 ns) it takes light to travel 12 in. in plexiglass ($\epsilon_r \approx 2.6$). Obviously, the gate can be placed anywhere such that it encompasses the desired main-material reflection and excludes the flange-edge reflection. A similar analysis can be performed for S_{21} resulting in time-domain-gated S-parameters. These can then be transformed to the frequency domain and used in the flanged-waveguide material-characterization technique reviewed above.

In addition to clearly showing the flange-edge reflections, Fig. 2 illustrates a much more important implication of the gating technique—the cross-sectional dimensions of the flanges (i.e., the footprint of the measurement system) can be made smaller (in this case, much smaller). The $|S_{11}|$ measurement depicted in Fig. 2 was measured at X-band (8.2–12.4 GHz). The range resolution of the measurement system can be calculated using the simple expression $\Delta R = \nu / (2B)$ where ν is the speed of light in the MUT and B is the bandwidth. For the measurement shown in Fig. 2, $\Delta R = 2.213$ cm, i.e., the 12 in. \times 12 in. flange size can be reduced to approximately 1 in. \times 1 in. and the flange-edge reflection will still be resolved. Note that the range resolution expression given above is for unwindowed frequency-domain data. If a window is used to suppress the sidelobes, ΔR will increase and larger flanges will be needed.

Before progressing to the experimental results to verify and demonstrate these concepts, a brief

summary is warranted. As originally designed, the flanged-waveguide material-characterization technique (reviewed in Section 2) was limited to lossy materials. This was necessary to ensure that the effects of two-way reflection error were mitigated. The time-gating technique presented in this paper improves the flanged-waveguide technique in two important ways. First, the time-gating technique allows low-loss materials to be measured effectively using the flanged-waveguide technique by gating out the flange-edge reflection. Second, the time-gating technique significantly reduces the required measurement footprint (cross-sectional dimensions of the flanges) of the flanged-waveguide technique by approximately an order of magnitude.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents experimental results applying the time-domain gating method discussed above to the flanged-waveguide material-characterization technique reviewed in Section 2. Measurements of plexiglass, using an Agilent Technologies E8362B vector network analyzer, were made at X-band using two flanged-waveguide apparatuses—one with 12 in. \times 12 in. \times 0.25 in. flanges and the other with 6 in. \times 6 in. \times 0.25 in. flanges. Both apparatuses were calibrated using a thru-reflect-line calibration [6]. The complex permittivity ϵ_r of plexiglass was determined by solving

$$\begin{cases} |S_{11}^{\text{thy}}(\epsilon_r; \omega) - S_{11}^{\text{meas}}(\omega)| \leq \delta \\ |S_{21}^{\text{thy}}(\epsilon_r; \omega) - S_{21}^{\text{meas}}(\omega)| \leq \delta \\ |S_{21}^{\text{thy}}(\epsilon_r; \omega) - S_{12}^{\text{meas}}(\omega)| \leq \delta \\ |S_{11}^{\text{thy}}(\epsilon_r; \omega) - S_{22}^{\text{meas}}(\omega)| \leq \delta \end{cases}, \quad (7)$$

where $\delta = 10^{-6}$, using Gauss-Newton nonlinear least squares.

Figures 3 and 4 show the complex permittivity results of plexiglass using 12 in. \times 12 in. flanges and 6 in. \times 6 in. flanges, respectively. Plotted in each figure are the results of the flanged-waveguide technique when the flange-edge reflection is not gated out (the no gate trace) and the results when the flange-edge reflection is removed (the gate trace). The time gate is placed at ± 1.15 ns in Fig. 3 and at ± 0.575 ns in Fig. 4. Also included on the figures are the complex permittivity values of plexiglass obtained using the parameter-extraction method developed by Nicolson, Ross, and Weir (NRW) [7, 8]. Note that only about 10 permittivity values (from 8.2–8.3 GHz) are available for the no gate traces. This is because

Figure 3: Complex permittivity of plexiglass measured using 12 in. \times 12 in. flanges.

Figure 4: Complex permittivity of plexiglass measured using 6 in. \times 6 in. flanges.

the flanged-waveguide technique does not converge for the no-gate data beyond 8.3 GHz. Even before 8.3 GHz, where solutions to (7) were found, the permittivity values are unstable. The gate traces, on the other hand, contain stable permittivity values across the whole frequency band, i.e., the flanged-waveguide technique converges for every data point using the gated S-parameters. Furthermore, the flanged-waveguide technique using the time-gated S-parameters compares well with NRW. The difference between the traces gets larger as frequency increases. It is expected that incorporating higher-order modes into the flanged-waveguide technique (recall that only the dominant mode is used here) will remedy this discrepancy.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, an elegant method is proposed to extend the flanged-waveguide technique (reviewed above) into the realm of low-loss materials. As dis-

cussed, the method involves time gating the measured S-parameters to remove the flange-edge reflection and thus mitigate two-way reflection error. The time-gating method is shown to improve the flange-waveguide technique by allowing low-loss materials to be measured and by reducing the required measurement footprint by approximately an order of magnitude. Lastly, the time-gate method is demonstrated experimentally by measuring the complex permittivity of plexiglass using 12 in. \times 12 in. and 6 in. \times 6 in. flanges. It is found that the time-gating method produces far superior results than those in which the technique is not used.

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